

THE ROLE OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN THE ECONOMY

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INTRODUCTION

The world economy fast paces with developed is going of our country this development to the process join with him together develop and change from the head in forgiveness our country big strength and high to development have to be for country socio-economic in his life achievement and disadvantages, opportunity and conditions out of consideration did not leave without of development intended degree and to the results reach ways find, of them maximum level use of this for necessary has been all measures done increase, most important task is considered That's it including this goal on the way national to the economy foreign investments active attraction reach and of them use efficiency increase important After all, to the economy foreign investments active attraction to do row positive to the effect is to achieve. Uzbekistan economy in development investment of projects efficient done increase in the place of import clicker commodity work release to the road put, modern technique and technologies current to export intended products work release development, development release acceleration through grow up going population work places with to provide is being achieved.

Highlight " Investments, first of all, our economy fundamentally to change, high to technologies based on new modern industry enterprises set up to do we directed and today mother so far away intended our work how that it is highly effective all of us seeing we are standing ".¹ Today's in the day our country each in the field many to achievements is reaching Our government done increasing reforms and this of reforms positive as a result our country main macroeconomic pointers constant respectively increase is being provided. Macroeconomic pointers country socio-economic potential pointer important is a factor.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In 2015-2019 the economy more reform make, structural change and diversification according to programs done increase in 2016 gross internal at the level of 7.8 % of the product high growth the pace provide enable gave The last 10 years inside GDP

¹ I.A.Karimov "Ona yurtimiz baxtu iqboli va buyuk kelajagi yo'lida xizmat qilish – eng oliy saodatdir". – T.: O'zbekiston, 2015.- 146 b

2 times the size increasingly sdi In 2016, "Focus Economics" international consulting of the company GDP growth pace according to the world countries in the rating Uzbekistan is 127 countries between seventh place took over 2016 year results village economy and industry product volumes - by 6.6 percent, construction - contract works - 12.5 percent, retail trade turnover - 14.4 percent, services - 12.5 percent grew up. Population soul per head GDP - 5.9 percent increased State budget gross internal to the product compared to 0.1 percentage in the amount surplus with execution done

External trade of circulation positive balance provided. Inflation level forecast from the parameters did not increase and 5.7 interest organize did

in 2016 stable high economic of growth main factors be lib the following service did :

- macroeconomic balance save stand up Economy subjects for tax of the load reduction, external trade of circulation positive the rest and 5.7 % low level reached inflation with one in line state of the budget to GDP at the level of 0.1% surplus provided;

- private property, business and small business interests protection to do and fast development. Entrepreneurship activities support and small work releases organize reach in order to, 2016 during small business subjects 16 trillion soums for around or past per year compared to 1.3 times a lot loans allocated, of which 3.3 trillion soums microcredits organize did Entrepreneurship environment formation, small business and private entrepreneurship development more encouragement and each bilaterally support according to acceptance being done measures 2016 32 thousand during new small business of subjects organize to be done the ground created As a result,, is small of business share In GDP up to 56.9 % (56.5% in 2015), in industry up to 45% (40.6%), in investments up to 40.3% (36.3%) and increased to 78.1% (77.9%) in employment;

- a village farm reform to make, modernization and diversification to do according to systematic of measures done increase village farm product 6.6 percent of the volume growth provided;

- services of the field, eng First of all, information communication and technologies based on modern service of types fast development GDP in the composition services field increase from 48.6 % in 2015 to 49.5% in 2016 take came

in 2016-2020 service show field development program done increase in 2016 during services 14.6 in the field a thousand new object organize reached 194 new ones household service show complexes to work dropped and 54 new ones hotel was built. As a result, it is shown services volume by 12.5%, that is including contact

and information services by 11.7%, financial services by 19.2%, motor transport services by 16.4%, trade by 14.7%, living and eating services increased by 11.7%.

- economic of growth stable high pace and population employment provide according to of programs done increase as well budget organizations employees monthly work 15% of salary, pensions and social increase of allowances by 12.1% because of of the population welfare and Gross real income increased by 11%. This is consumption demand encouragement measures with one in line retail trade circulation increase in volume by 14.4 % provided.

In our country done being increased reforms, this reforms deepening and the country modernization regarding our government by done being increased practical measures and programs our country economy descriptive main macroeconomic pointers constant respectively increase, that's it with together, the country socio-economic development in providing important importance occupation reached is coming Our country main macroeconomic pointers not only quantitative in terms of perhaps quality increasing in terms of is coming That is in our country work issued gross internal product the content is also quality in terms of changed, gross internal product in the composition industry and service show share year after year increased is coming Of this obvious the proof above table through let's see can

of 2022 Uzbekistan in the Republic economic and social areas development for total financing sources 121.8 trillion. soum mastered. 11.0 in dollar equivalent billion USD. mastered in 2021 suitable to the period compared to 109.4% organize did of 2022 main to capital 56.8% of investments or 69.1 trillion. soum attraction done funds at the expense of funded if, enterprise, organization and of the population own funds 43.2 % or 52.7 trillion. soum was financed. Total investments in size, centered financing sources at the expense of funded main to capital of investments share of 2021 suitable period per share by 6.1 % points decreased by 12.0% or 14.6 trillion. soum organize did

Foreign investment and loans, billion soums²

2022 year Uzbekistan in the Republic again work in the industry foreign investment and loans weighty 23,293.8 bln. soum or total main to capital mastered 48.5% of investments organize did Electric and gas with provide activity in type this the indicator is 5,721.2 billion soum or total foreign investment and 11.9% of loans note did

Mining in the industry a total of 7,918.0 billion soums or republic according to total investments 6.5% of its volume has been absorbed being his 4.2% of its composition or 5,085.0 billion. Sum raw oil and natural gas digging release to the field is relevant.

² Uzbekistan Statistics Committee www.stat.uz

Economical activity types according to foreign investments and loans composition, in %³

Suitable, decentralized financing sources 107,2 from the account trln. soum or total 88.0% of investments will be absorbed in 2021 suitable period to the indicator by 6.1 % points increased. of 2022 January-June months enterprise and of organizations own funds at the expense of funded main to capital investments - 41.5 trillion. soum or total main to capital 34.1% of investments organize did

Directly straight away foreign investments at the expense of funded investments at the expense of Uzbekistan Republic 16.0 trillion according to soum, or in 2021 suitable period to the indicator by 1.1 % points decreased without total in investments share by 13.2% equal to investments mastered. Main to capital of investments financing sources according to in the composition the most high growth

³ Uzbekistan Statistics Committee www.stat.uz

pace enterprise and of organizations own funds at the expense of funded in investments observed in 2021 suitable to the period by 135.0 % increased note done Not guaranteed and another foreign investment and loans 26.8 from the account trln. soum investments absorbed, total main to capital investments in size share of 2021 suitable period to the indicator by 0.2 percentage points decreased by 22.0% organize did.

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